

IN THE NAME OF GOD

Topic :Gene Therapy
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1) What is a gene?

A gene is the basic physical and functional unit of heredity. Genes are made up of DNA. Some genes act as instructions to make molecules called proteins. However, many genes do not code for proteins. In humans, genes vary in size from a few hundred DNA bases to more than 2 million bases. An international research effort called the Human Genome Project, which worked to determine the sequence of the human genome and identify the genes that it contains, estimated that humans have between 20,000 and 25,000 genes.

Every person has two copies of each gene, one inherited from each parent. Most genes are the same in all people, but a small number of genes (less than 1 percent of the total) are slightly different between people. Alleles are forms of the same gene with small differences in their sequence of DNA bases. These small differences contribute to each person's unique physical features.

Scientists keep track of genes by giving them unique names. Because gene names can be long, genes are also assigned symbols, which are short combinations of letters (and sometimes numbers) that represent an abbreviated version of the gene name. For example, a gene on chromosome 7 that has been associated with cystic fibrosis is called the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator; its symbol is CFTR.

2) What is a mutation?

Mutations are changes in the genetic sequence, and they are a main cause of diversity among organisms. These changes occur at many different levels, and they can have widely differing consequences. In biological systems that are capable of reproduction, we must first focus on whether they are heritable; specifically, some mutations affect only the individual that carries them, while others affect all of the carrier organism's offspring, and further descendants. *A mutation is a change that occurs in our DNA sequence, either due to mistakes when the DNA is copied or as the result of environmental factors such as UV light and cigarette smoke.*

3) What is gene therapy?

Gene therapy is an experimental technique that uses genes to treat or prevent disease. In the future, this technique may allow doctors to treat a disorder by inserting a gene into a patient's cells instead of using drugs or surgery. Researchers are testing several approaches to gene therapy, including:

Replacing a mutated gene that causes disease with a healthy copy of the gene.

Inactivating, or "knocking out," a mutated gene that is functioning improperly.

Introducing a new gene into the body to help fight a disease.

Although gene therapy is a promising treatment option for a number of diseases (including inherited disorders, some types of cancer, and certain viral infections), the technique remains risky and is still under study to make sure that it will be safe and effective. Gene therapy is currently being tested only for diseases that have no other cures.

Gene therapy has been studied for more than 40 years and can help stop or slow the effects of disease on the most basic level of the human body—our genes. Gene therapy is the use of genetic material in the treatment or prevention of disease.

3) What is gene therapy?

So, now that we know what genes are, how can they be used to help fight cancer? If a gene becomes damaged, this damage is called a mutation. This can lead to a gene not working properly and a cell growing uncontrollably. When cells grow too quickly or uncontrollably, cancer can form. Keep in mind that developing a cancer is not quite as simple as this, but requires a complex series of multiple mutations. These mutations may be caused by things like smoking, the environment, or they may be inherited (passed down from your parents). It makes sense that if we could repair these mutations, we could possibly stop a cancer from starting. The question is, how do we do this?

Researchers are testing several ways of using gene therapy in the treatment of cancer:

- Replace missing or non-functioning (non-working) genes. For example, p53 is a gene called a "tumor suppressor gene." Its job is just that: to suppress (prevent or stop) tumors from forming. Cells that are missing this gene, or have a non-functioning copy because of a mutation, may be "fixed" by adding functioning copies of p53 to the cell.
- Oncogenes are mutated genes that can cause either a new cancer or the spread of an existing cancer (metastasis). By stopping the function of these genes, the cancer and/or its spread may be stopped.

- Use the body's own immune system by inserting genes into cancer cells that then trigger the body to attack the cancer cells as foreign invaders.

- Insert genes into cancer cells so that chemotherapy, radiation therapy, or hormone therapies can attack the cancer cells more easily.

Viral DNA New Gene Viral DNA

Modified DNA injected into vector

Vector binds to cell membrane

Vector is packaged in vesicle

Vesicle breaks down releasing vector

Vector injects new gene into nucleus

Cell makes protein using new gene

Gene therapy using an adenovirus vector

4) How does gene therapy work?

Gene therapy is designed to introduce genetic material into cells to compensate for abnormal genes or to make a beneficial protein. If a mutated gene causes a necessary protein to be faulty or missing, gene therapy may be able to introduce a normal copy of the gene to restore the function of the protein.

A gene that is inserted directly into a cell usually does not function. Instead, a carrier called a vector is genetically engineered to deliver the gene. Certain viruses are often used as vectors because they can deliver the new gene by infecting the cell. The viruses are modified so they can't cause disease when used in people. Some types of virus, such as retroviruses, integrate their genetic material (including the new gene) into a chromosome in the human cell. Other viruses, such as adenoviruses, introduce their DNA into the nucleus of the cell, but the DNA is not integrated into a chromosome.

The vector can be injected or given intravenously (by IV) directly into a specific tissue in the body, where it is taken up by individual cells. Alternately, a sample of the patient's cells can be removed and exposed to the vector in a laboratory setting. The cells containing the vector are then returned to the patient. If the treatment is successful, the new gene delivered by the vector will make a functioning protein. Researchers must overcome many technical challenges before gene therapy will be a practical approach to treating disease. For example, scientists must find better ways to deliver genes and target them to particular cells. They must also ensure that new genes are precisely controlled by the body.

Virus enters cell through membrane

Virus is packaged in vesicle

Increasing acidity causes release of pentons

Penton toxicity breaches vesicle

Gene Therapy Using an Adenovirus Vector

Nuclear Pore

Nucleus

Virus disassembles and delivers DNA into nucleus

Nuclear Pore

mRNA

RNA Polymerase

Genetic information from the new gene is transferred to a molecule called mRNA, which serves as a blueprint for protein production

5) How is gene therapy given?

Gene delivery is one of the biggest challenges of gene therapy. You can imagine it would be hard to actually inject these genes into the tiny cells, so a carrier, or a "vector," is used to do this. Typically, viruses are used as the vectors. The virus vector must be genetically changed to carry human DNA. These viruses are like those that cause the common cold, only they are "deactivated" (turned off) so that they will not cause the patient to actually get the cold.

In some cases, some cells are taken from the patient and the virus is exposed to the cells in the laboratory. The virus with the desired gene attached finds its way into the cells. These cells are allowed to grow in the laboratory. The grown cells are then given back to the patient by intravenous (IV) infusion or are injected into a body cavity (i.e. the lung) or a tumor.

In other cases, the vector with the attached gene is directly inserted into the patient by intravenous infusion or is injected into a body cavity or a tumor. Once the gene has reached the cell, it must go to the cell's nucleus (where the DNA, or genetic code is) and combine with the human genetic material. Then it needs to be "turned on," to produce the protein product of that gene. For gene delivery to be successful, the protein that is produced must work properly. As you can see, that's a number of steps that need to go right for the therapy to work.

6) Gene augmentation therapy

This is used to treat diseases caused by a mutation that stops a gene from producing a functioning product, such as a protein?

This therapy adds DNA containing a functional version of the lost gene back into the cell.

The new gene produces a functioning product at sufficient levels to replace the protein that was originally missing.

This is only successful if the effects of the disease are reversible or have not resulted in lasting damage to the body.

For example, this can be used to treat loss of function disorders such as cystic fibrosis by introducing a functional copy of the gene to correct the disease (see illustration below).

7) Gene inhibition therapy

Suitable for the treatment of infectious diseases, cancer and inherited disease caused by inappropriate gene activity.

The aim is to introduce a gene whose product either:

inhibits the expression of another gene

interferes with the activity of the product of another gene.

The basis of this therapy is to eliminate the activity of a gene that encourages the growth of disease-related cells.

For example, cancer is sometimes the result of the over-activation of an oncogene[?] (gene which stimulates cell growth). So, by eliminating the activity of that oncogene through gene inhibition therapy, it is possible to prevent further cell growth and stop the cancer in its tracks.

8) Killing of specific cells

Suitable for diseases such as cancer that can be treated by destroying certain groups of cells.

The aim is to insert DNA into a diseased cell that causes that cell to die.

This can be achieved in one of two ways:

the inserted DNA contains a “suicide” gene that produces a highly toxic product which kills the diseased cell

the inserted DNA causes expression of a protein that marks the cells so that the diseased cells are attacked by the body’s natural immune system.

It is essential with this method that the inserted DNA is targeted appropriately to avoid the death of cells that are functioning normally.

Killing of specific cells

9) How is DNA transfer done?

A section of DNA/gene containing instructions for making a useful protein is packaged within a vector, usually a virus[?], bacterium[?] or plasmid[?]. The vector acts as a vehicle to carry the new DNA into the cells of a patient with a genetic disease.

Once inside the cells of the patient, the DNA/gene is expressed by the cell's normal machinery leading to production of the therapeutic protein and treatment of the patient's disease.

10) Challenges of gene therapy

Delivering the gene to the right place and switching it on:
it is crucial that the new gene reaches the right cell
delivering a gene into the wrong cell would be inefficient and could also cause health problems for the patient
even once the right cell has been targeted the gene has to be turned on
cells sometimes obstruct this process by shutting down genes that are showing unusual activity.

Avoiding the immune response:

The role of the immune system is to fight off intruders.

Sometimes new genes introduced by gene therapy are considered potentially-harmful intruders.

This can spark an immune response in the patient, that could be harmful to them.

Scientists therefore have the challenge of finding a way to deliver genes without the immune system 'noticing'.

This is usually by using vectors that are less likely to trigger an immune response.

11) Somatic Cell Gene Therapy

Somatic cell gene therapy involves the placement of a human gene into a living person's somatic cells—cells that do not produce the eggs and sperm that in turn produce the next generation. Somatic cell gene therapy would aim to cure a disease only in the patient, not in the patient's descendants. It was initially conceived as introducing a properly functioning copy of a gene into a person who had a genetic disease as a result of inheriting only improperly functioning copies. Different types of somatic cell gene therapy have since been investigated for the treatment of diseases that are not primarily caused by inherited genes, such as AIDS and cancer. Over 100 clinical trials of somatic cell gene therapy have taken place; very few have, thus far, shown any success.

The genetic aspects of somatic cell gene therapy have been largely uncontroversial. In essence, the gene therapy is merely another drug delivery system, a different way to get a normal human protein to the right place in the body. Somatic cell gene therapy therefore stands in the same position as most experimental therapies. Like such therapies, it has prompted concerns that desperate patients are not truly giving informed consent and that the possible benefits of the treatment are exaggerated. Gene therapy may face the latter problem to a greater extent than most experimental treatments because of the exaggerated public view of the power of anything genetic.

12) *In vivo* and *Ex vivo* Approaches to Gene Therapy

In vivo delivery

In vivo gene therapy refers to direct delivery of genetic material either intravenously (through an IV) or locally to a specific organ (eg, directly into the eye).

In vivo gene therapy works through the help of a vector, which directly inserts functional copies of a gene into target cells to treat a mutated or missing gene. *In vivo* delivery of gene therapy has been proven in many areas of research.

Some of the currently approved gene therapies deliver genetic material *in vivo*. Targeted *in vivo* gene therapy will continue to evolve as scientists continue to refine methods of gene delivery.

Ex vivo delivery

Ex vivo gene therapy refers to the process of removing specific cells from a person, genetically altering them in a laboratory, and then transplanting them back into the person.

Ex vivo gene therapy works by genetically modifying a patient's stem cells, which then replace target cells that have a missing or malfunctioning gene.

Today, *ex vivo* gene therapy is most frequently applied to hematopoietic stem cells (HSCs); this is used to treat blood and immunological diseases as well as genetic diseases that affect tissues and organs that can be reached by blood cells.

13) Germ Line Gene Therapy

Germ line gene therapy is much more controversial. It would introduce 'normal' human genes into the eggs or sperm of parents, or into the fertilized egg or early embryo of the offspring. The goal would be to change the eventual child's genetic inheritance. This could be done in order to avoid a genetic disease or in order to introduce an 'enhancing' genetic variation. There have been no trials of human germ line gene therapy; indeed, there is an informal moratorium in the scientific community on trying such experiments in humans.

14) MovieAbout gene therapy

**Thank you for your attention
Professor Dr. Barani**

**Resources:
PUBMED
GOOGLESCHOLAR
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www.oncolink.org**

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